

THE INFLUENCE OF DISTANCE LEARNING ON MSU-SULU 4TH YEAR BA ELS STUDENTS' IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE COMPREHENSION

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ABSTRACT

This study is a qualitative research, where there were a distribution of survey-questionnaires to the respondents. This study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design. This was conducted at College of Art and Sciences, Department of languages in Mindanao State University-Sulu. There were 40 BA ELS students served as a respondents and participant of this study. The data were treated with the mean, standard deviation, frequency, percentage and Pearson-Product correlation. The purpose of this study was to know the influence of distance learning on MSU-SULU 4th year BA ELS students' in the English language comprehension of Mindanao State University-Sulu. Purposive sampling design was utilized to gather the data from the respondents. There were Three (3) research problem were posted: [1] what is the influence of distance learning in the English language comprehension among fourth year BA ELS students of Mindanao State University-Sulu? [2] What are the effect of distance learning in the English language comprehension? [3] Is there a significant relationship between influence of distance learning and its effect in the English language comprehension? The findings revealed that the respondents of the study were fourth year BA ELS students at Mindanao State University-Sulu, College of Arts and Sciences. Majority of the respondents were moderately influenced by the distance learning and its effect in the English language comprehension. The correlation appears that there is **no significant** relationship between the influenced of distance learning and its effect in the English language comprehension

among fourth year BA ELS students in Mindanao State University-Sulu. Using **Pearson-correlation**, the p-value is **0.030** which is less than **0.05**, meaning the **null hypothesis of no relationship is rejected**. In conclusion, based from the findings that the respondents from Jolo Sulu were highly influenced by the distance learning. In fact, they are near to the school. Hence, they were preferred to enroll in distance learning program. The respondents were **moderately influenced** by the influence of distance learning in the English language comprehension. While, the respondents were **highly influenced** on the effect of distance learning in term of reading and understanding English language.

Keywords: *Distance Learning, BA ELS, MSU-SULU, English Language comprehension*

INTRODUCTION

As the traditional classroom and face-to-face learning are disintegrated due to pandemic existence it changes the way we live, the demand for more flexible learning or distance learning opportunity also increased. To cope up with the changing world, the university all over the world especially in the Philippines shifted to distance learning in order to address these needs. It means, As the pandemic continued to spread, the government applied distance learning to provide basic learning to the students even they are not going to the classroom environment. The basic definition of distance learning considers that the teachers and the students are separated in the spatial dimension and that this Z is filled by using technological resources, Casarotti, et al (2002). It means the distance learning basically the students and teachers are not using traditional which is the face-to-face classroom scenario. They are far from each other without interaction. It is the process of using technology to access any tasks and activities. This is now the latest trends of the educational system of the current situation happening across the globe. A new change that was introduced to us, but just we must embrace this new changes, for us to cope with the latest trends and styles in educational system. This mean embracing new trends, tends to become globally equipped and ready to face new challenges and changes.

A modality of learning delivery known as "distance learning" involves students and teachers who are separated by distance during the teaching process. Quinones (2020) distinguishes three types of this modality: TV/radio-based instruction, online distance learning (ODL), and modular distance learning (MDL). The most often used kind of distance learning is modular. According to a Department of Education (DepEd) survey, parents whose children are enrolled in this academic year most prefer to learn through printed and digital modules. This learning modality is currently used by all public schools in the Philippines. In this sense, public and private schools across the nation employ distance learning as a common program.

An increasingly popular alternative to traditional classroom settings, distance education has played a significant role in creating a more competitive environment in higher education. Previously considered an experimental substitute for traditional

university education, distant learning has gained unprecedented recognition and growth, transforming into a distinct higher education sector, according to Merisotis & Phipps (1999). At this time, colleges and universities all throughout the nation were using distant learning. This plays a crucial role in helping students acquire knowledge in the new normal system and adapt to the latest trends and learning styles in education.

The Department of Education (DepEd) introduced modular distance learning as the new standard of education that the Philippines has adopted for the benefit of all Filipino students and to ensure educational continuity. The utilization of learning modules promotes autonomous study. Encouraging students to better self-study and develop their learning skills is one of the advantages of modular remote learning for training. They now feel accountable for completing the tasks in the modules. According to Nardo, M.T.B. (2017), they are empowered and learning how to learn. One of the additional benefits of modular classes was that they allowed students to learn from home. Provide teachers and staff members with a range of options and flexibility while also enhancing the adaptability of printed teaching materials.

Research Questions

This study is sought to determine the influence of distance learning on MSU-SULU 4th year BA ELS students' in the English language comprehension. This answers the following questions:

1. What are the influence of distance learning in the English language comprehension among fourth year BA ELS students in Mindanao State University-Sulu?
2. What are the effects of distance learning in the English language comprehension?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the influence of distance learning and its effect in the English language comprehension?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized descriptive-survey research design to determine the influenced of distance learning in the English language comprehension of fourth year BAELS students. The said design described the possible consequences of implementing the distance learning program.

This design used to make the details about the topic. The researchers made description, to state the influence of the distance learning in the English language

comprehension. They will utilize this design to make sense about their doubt in the field of their study.

The design mentioned above is the best design related to the topic. With this the problem stated appropriately and accurately. This method suited most to this field. At the same time, this is the available design used to conduct this study, to able to describe and to completely observe the possible influence and effect of distance learning in the field of English language comprehension.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at Mindanao State University-Sulu. It is one of the most populated schools in province of Sulu. The creation of MSU- Sulu is one of the greatest educational developments in the province of Sulu. The establishment of MSU- Sulu provides the Tausog young generation the chances to pursue higher education. The courses offered ranging from two year technology courses in Fisheries and Agriculture. Others are Bachelor Degrees in Public Administration, Arts and Sciences, Education, Agriculture, Business Administration and Computer Science. Courses also offers are the Masteral Degrees in Education, Public Administration and Islamic Studies. Doctoral Program in Philosophy of Education is now available.

MSU- Sulu was established on February 11, 1974 that was made operational by the strength of the Board of Regents Resolution No. 860, as amended to provide a well-meaning education to the people of the war ravaged province (Sulu) and this will strive to pursue the traditional function of the University such as classroom instruction, quality research, and extension program.

Respondents of the Study

The participants of this study are the fourth year BAELS students of Mindanao State University-Sulu. There are two (2) section in fourth year level with a total of 78 students. The respondents are given the survey questionnaire to determine their ideas about the influence of distance learning in the English language comprehension. The said respondents are distributed with regard to their field of studies. The researchers make a distribution to easily access them.

The researchers carefully select the students as their respondents to create a clear and accurate data. It is in the purpose of determining the objectives and purpose of the said research.

Table 1. Distribution of respondents by section

Section	POPULATION	Sample
A	38	20
B	40	20
Total	78	40

The table above showed the distribution of respondents by section. It implies that the students from section A is few in number compare to section B. in this sense, the section A student were select at least 20 from them serves as a respondent. As for section B student were select also 20 from them as a respondent. Out of 78 students under the BAELS course, there are only 40 selected as respondents in conducting this study.

Research Instrument

The research instrument use in this study are consists of two parts. The 15 items of part 1 is used to determine the effect of distance learning in the English language comprehension, and other 15 items for part two is utilized to find out the influence of distance learning to the fourth year BAELS students in Mindanao State University-Sulu. The survey questionnaire will validate by the adviser from Mindanao State University-Sulu in College of Arts and Sciences (CAS) specifically in Department of Languages. The basis for the validation of the questionnaire is for content and content accuracy, clarity and appropriateness.

The instruments especially the questionnaires will be distributed to the respondents to collect their perception about the topic. This serve as a guide of the researchers to gather the information needed.

The two (2) parts questionnaire composed of 30 items. The respondents' response to every statement would rate using 5-points scale, and it will categorize as follows:

Strongly agree (5), agree (4), undecided (3), disagree (2), and strongly disagree (1)

Table 2. Scoring procedure on the influence of distance learning and its effect in the English language comprehension

Range	Scale	Response	Qualifying statement
4.20-5.00	5	Strongly agree	Very highly influence
3.40-4.19	4	Agree	Highly influence
2.60-3.39	3	undecided	Moderately influence
1.80-2.59	2	Disagree	Slightly influence
1.00-1.79	1	Strong disagree	Not totally influence

Sampling procedure

The sampling procedure use is the purposive sampling. The researcher used sampling procedure to gather the data from the respondents. This procedure is the appropriate technique to collect information from the respondents. The researchers are intentionally selected those students as their respondents. After that, they distributed the survey questionnaire.

Using this sampling procedure, the researchers easily obtained the data needed for their respondents.

Data gathering procedure

The researcher followed the proper protocol in conducting the study. First, the researchers asked permission from their adviser and made the letter to the office of the Dean of College of Arts and Sciences at Mindanao State University-Sulu.

The researchers also asked permission to the selected students to be their respondent before distributing the survey questionnaires in conducting the study. After accomplishing the necessary procedure, the researchers proceed in conducting the study to obtain the needed data in their study.

Statistical treatment of data

To answer the problem one (1) and two (2), the means and standard deviation, frequency percentage will utilize to determine the influence of distance learning in the English language comprehension and the factors that influenced the students to enroll in distance learning program.

To answer the problem three (3) the Pearson product-moment correlations used to determine the correlation of the influence of distance learning and its effect in the English language comprehension.

The statistical treatment of data used to identify the influence of distance learning in the English language comprehension among fourth year BAELS students in Mindanao State University-Sulu. The said statistical tool is the correct instruments used to be able to determine the purpose of the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Address and Status

The table 1 categorize the status and the address of the respondents by municipalities as follows: Indanan Sulu, Jolo Sulu, Patikul Sulu, Omar Sulu, Parang Sulu and Talipao Sulu. As shown in the table, there were 6 or 15% respondents from Municipality of Indanan, 13 or 32.5% from municipality of Jolo, 11 or 27.5% from Patikul Sulu, 2 or 5% from Omar municipality and Municipality of Parang and Omar have 4 or 10% respondents each. It means that the respondents coming from Jolo, Sulu have highly influenced by the distance learning program.

Therefore, they wanted to experience how this program change and develop their skills and abilities.

Respondents information	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1. Address		
Jolo Sulu	13	32.5
Patikul Sulu	11	27.5
Indanan Sulu	6	15
Parang Sulu	4	10
Talipao Sulu	4	10
Omar Sulu	2	5
Total	40	100
2. Status		
Single	39	97.5
Married	1	2.5
Total	40	100

In term of status, it was categorized into single and married. As shown in the table above, there were 39 or 97.5% respondents/students who are single and only 1 or 2.5%

respondent is married. It means, that the students with no spouse are highly influenced to enrol in the distance learning program rather than married student.

Table 2. Educational background and gender

Respondents information	Frequency (f)	Percentage %
3.Educational Background		
Fourth year BAELS	40	100
Total	40	100
4. Gender		
Female	29	72.5
Male	11	27.5
Total	40	100

In terms of educational background of the respondents, it is clearly shown in the table above that all of the respondents were fourth year BA ELS students. Out of 79 students under the Bachelor of Arts in English language Studies, 40 or 100% of them were utilized to determine the influence of distance learning in the English language comprehension. It is implied that the researchers were just 40 selected students as a respondents in this study.

The gender was categorized as follows; Male and female. As presented in the table above, 11 or 27.5% male students utilized in the study while the female was 29 or 72.5%. It implies that the female students are highly influenced in the distance learning. And also, as what we have observed nowadays, female have greater number than male. No doubt that most of the respondents were female students of the BA ELS program.

There were 15 items survey questionnaires used to determine the influence of distance learning in the English language comprehension.

Based from the data presented in table 3 there were 5 items obtained higher mean score under agree that categorized as follows: *Online learning can influence student in learning English language* (4). *Distance learning is one way which student learn individually* (3). *Distance learning can motivate students to do the task* (5). *COVID-19 can leads the students to enroll in modular distance learning program* (1). *Further, Distance learning motivate students to do the task well* (2). It means that the mean score shows that most of the respondents were highly influenced by the distance learning.

Considering the standard deviation the whole items showed the heterogeneity of the responses. It means, the standard variation are widely dispersed and there were variation of the responses.

This shift has been occurring in all field of education, including English language instruction, Vovides, et al (2007). It implies that online learning is useful in learning English language.

There were 8 items classified as undecided response as follows: *Distance learning can provide wide learning to the students* (12). *Modular distance learning can improve learning English comprehension of the students* (13). *Online learning is the easiest way in understanding English language* (7). *Online learning is suitable in learning English language* (9). *Students in distance learning are more active than face-to-face classes* (10). *Distance learning provide enjoyment to the students* (8). *Distance learning can influenced the students to become participative* (11). *Distance learning increase English language comprehension* (6).

The mean score show that the respondents were moderately influenced by the distance learning since they were undecided on those survey questionnaire by considering the standard deviation there was depicted heterogeneity in all items. It means, there is a variation of the response from the respondents.

There were 2 items survey questionnaires classified as disagree response as follows: *Distance learning is the right way to learn and gain more knowledge* (14). *Distance learning is more effective than face-to-face learning* (15). The means score shows that the respondents were slightly influenced by the distance learning. In term of standard deviation, it indicates that the response were heterogeneous. It means that there is a variation or difference in the distribution.

The overall mean indicates that the respondents were undecided on the influence of the distance learning in the English language comprehension. An overall standard deviation shows that there were a variation or spread of scores based on the rating of the respondents.

Table 3 The Influence of the distance learning in the English language comprehension

	Means	S.D	Descriptive Interpretation
1. COVID-19 can leads the students to enroll in modular distance learning program.	3.85	0.975	Agree
2. Distance learning motivate students to do the task well.	3.73	1.062	Agree
3. Distance learning is one way learning which student learn individually.	3.60	0.955	Agree

4. Online learning can influence student in learning English language.	3.45	0.904	Agree
5. Distance learning can inspire students to do the task.	3.43	1.083	Agree
6. Distance learning increase English language comprehension.	3.18	1.035	Undecided
7. Online learning is the easiest way in understanding English language.	3.10	1.033	Undecided
8. Distance learning provide enjoyment to the students.	2.98	1.143	Undecided
9. Online learning is suitable in learning English language.	2.85	0.949	Undecided
10. Students in distance learning are more active than face-to-face classes.	2.70	1.224	Undecided
11. Distance learning can influence the students to become participative.	2.65	1.051	Undecided
12. Distance learning can provide wide learning to the students.	2.63	0.740	Undecided
13. Modular distance learning can improve learning English comprehension of the students.	2.60	0.841	Undecided
14. Distance learning is the right way to learn and gain more knowledge.	2.53	0.933	Disagree
15. Distance learning is more effective than face-to-face learning.	1.95	0.846	Disagree
Overall	3.01	1.104	Undecided

*Legend

- 1.00-1.79 = 1 (Strong disagree)
- 1.80-2.59 = 2 (Disagree)
- 2.60-3.39 = 3 (Undecided)
- 3.40-4.19 = 4 (Agree)
- 4.20-5.00 = 5 (Strongly agree)

The 15 items developed survey questionnaires were used to determine the effect of the distance learning in the English language comprehension on the fourth year BA ELS students.

As shown in table 4, there were 9 items that obtained a higher means score and categorized as follows: *Modular distance learning can increase student's motivation in reading and understanding English language (22). Distance learning is one of the stressful way of learning (20). Hopelessness in distance learning lead to failure of learning English language (23). Online learning can change the behavior of the students in learning English language comprehension (17). Modular learning can lead to student works under pressure in various activities in English comprehension (20). Distance learning decreases student's interaction with their instructors (24). Distance learning*

deconstruct student's skills (18). Additionally, Modular distance learning makes it difficult to students in learning English language (16). Modules can affect English language comprehension of the students (28).

This means that most of the respondents were highly influenced by the distance learning. Considering the standard deviation, it was indicated that the responses were heterogeneous. It connotes that there is a variation in terms of distribution of the responses as rated by the respondents.

Table 4 The effects of distance learning in the English language comprehension

	Means	S.D	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Modular distance learning makes it difficult to students in learning English language.	3.83	1.083	Agree
2. Online learning can change the behavior of the students in learning English language comprehension	3.75	0.927	Agree
3. Distance learning destruct student's skills.	3.70	1.091	Agree
4. Distance learning is one of the stressful way of learning.	3.68	1.228	Agree
5. Modular learning can lead to student work under pressure in various activities in English comprehension.	3.68	1.071	Agree
6. Modules can enhance English language comprehension of the students.	3.68	1.047	Agree
7. Modular distance learning can increase student's motivation in reading and understanding English language.	3.50	0.987	Agree
8. Hopelessness in distance learning lead to failure of learning English language.	3.48	1.037	Agree
9. Distance learning decreases student's interaction with their instructors.	3.45	1.358	Agree
10. Distance learning decrease the number of learners	3.38	1.192	Undecided
11. Distance learning decrease student's eagerness in learning English language.	3.23	1.097	Undecided
12. Online distance learning makes students unconscious in English language.	3.10	1.057	Undecided
13. Modules can affect English language comprehension of the students.	2.95	0.986	Undecided
14. Distance learning can make students intelligent.	2.95	0.904	Undecided
15. Distance learning can enhance collaborative skills of the students.	2.90	1.033	Undecided

As show in the table, there were six (6) items under the undecided responses categorized as follows: *Distance learning can enhance collaborative skills of the students* (Item 30). *Modules can affect English language comprehension of the students* (21). *Distance learning can make students intelligent* (29). *Distance learning decrease student's eagerness in learning English language* (26). *Distance learning decrease the number of learners* (25). *Further, Online distance learning makes students' unconscious in learning English language* (27).

This means that the respondents were moderately influenced by the distance learning. It implies that they were undecided based on the response given. In term of standard deviation, it showed the response were heterogeneous. It signified that there is a variation of the responses.

The overall mean shows that the respondents were highly influenced by the distance learning in the English language comprehension. An overall standard deviation implies that the response were dispersed. This means that there was a variation or difference on the distributions of the responses rated by the respondents.

Table 5 Relationship of influence and effect

Correlations			
		Influence	Effect
Influence	Pearson Correlation	1	.343*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.030
	N	40	40
Effect	Pearson Correlation	.343*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.030	
	N	40	40

As gleaned from the mean value for the relationship of the two (2) variables, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship of the influence of distance learning on MSU-SULU 4th year BA ELS students' in the English language comprehension tested at $p < 0.05$ level of significance. The result revealed that the main influence has a significant relationship, the null hypothesis is rejected. The findings simply shows that the influenced of the respondents to take distance learning program and its effect on the English language comprehension has a significant relationship.

This study determined the influence of distance learning on MSU-SULU 4th year BA ELS students' in the English language comprehension. Its purpose is to know how distance learning can be effective in learning English language. It was determined by the influence and effect among fourth year BA ELS students.

In the major findings of the study the respondents were **moderately influenced** by the distance learning in the English language comprehension and it obtained a lower mean score. There is a significance relationship between the influence of distance learning and its effect in the English language comprehension.

Conclusions

The following conclusion were concluded from the findings of the study:

1. The respondents from Jolo Sulu were highly influenced by the distance learning. In fact, they are near the school. Hence, they preferred to enroll in distance learning program.
2. The respondents were **moderately influenced** by the influence of distance learning in the English language comprehension.
 - 2.1. Distance learning is one way in which student learn individually and COVID-19 was consider as to causes highly to influence the respondents to enroll in distance learning. Therefore, with this reason the respondents were **highly influenced** by the distance learning.
 - 2.2. Online learning can influenced student in learning English language and Distance learning motivate students to do their task well, it may contribute to highly influence on the part of the respondents to enroll in distance learning. Therefore, because of the motivation the respondents were enrolled in the distance learning.
 - 2.3. The respondents were **moderately influenced** by the modular and online distance learning in terms of learning English language. Thus, they believed that the distance learning cannot totally support in the learning process of the students.
 - 2.4. The respondents were **slightly influenced** on the distance learning as stated as distance learning is the right way to learn and gain more knowledge and it is effective than face-to-face. Therefore, the respondents were clearly experienced that distance learning is not an effective program to use in order to provide learning to the students.
3. The respondents were **moderately influenced** by the effect of the distance learning in the English language comprehension.
 - 3.1. The respondents were highly influenced on the effect of distance learning in term of reading and understanding English language. They also feel stressed in engaging in distance learning. Therefore, they agree that distance learning can be a means in motivating them to read and understand English language.
 - 3.2. Distance learning decrease student's interaction result to destruction of their skills. It was described as **moderately influenced**. Thus, the respondents believed

that distance learning can lost their opportunities to use their skills. In fact, they have less interaction with their teachers and classmates.

3.3. The respondents were ***moderately influenced*** on the effect of distance learning as stated that distance learning can make students brilliant. Therefore, they believed that distance learning cannot support in learning and acquiring knowledge and skills.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendation are suggested:

1. It is further suggested students in distance learning should study hard to become more responsible, dedicated and equipped with the right knowledge even in the time of pandemic. They should at least manage their time in doing this. The young generation of today are ready to face these new changes and engaged themselves to the new program.
2. Government should think a possible solution to support the learning of the students rather than distance learning. It is further suggested that the face-to-face classes must be reform and regain to address the learning failure of the students. Because the distance learning is not an effective way to be used due to the limited access and it is new to us. The government must address this problem to provide enough learning to the students, in a very convenient way.
3. Teachers should use effective techniques by this time in order to enhance the learning of the students especially for those who have the low learning ability. It is suggested that they must consider the students who have the learning ability problem to make it easy for the learners to acquire knowledge and to boost their learning ability even during this time.
4. It is further suggested that schools, universities and other institutions should provide sufficient internet connection to the students to support their learning. The school head should make a request to the authorities and other higher positions to develop the needs of the schools as well as the teachers and students.
5. Parents should take part in supporting and providing the needs of their children to assure the progress and development in terms of their study. The role of parents is very crucial most especially of giving supports (be it physically, mentally and financially), eventually boost their motivations and it gives them a sense of being loved and provided with all the things they need.

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Compliance with Ethical Standards

In this study, the ethical care of all participants—especially the teachers at Mindanao State University-Sulu—is of utmost importance. While researching significant topics, the researcher made a consistent effort to uphold the respondents' right to privacy.

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